

**THE ROLE OF MEDIA ORGANISATIONS IN THE SAFETY OF JOURNALISTS
COVERING BOKO HARAM INSURGENCY IN NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the role of media organisations in the safety of journalists covering the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria. The research sought to assess the nature of safety measures media organisations provide for journalists they send to cover the activities of the Boko Haram insurgents and to identify the safety routine measures journalists adopted before fieldwork. The Protection Motivation and the Risk Compensation theories were reviewed and used as theoretical framework for the study. To achieve these objectives, a qualitative research approach was used as a means of getting valuable data. In-depth Interview (IDI) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were selected as the methods for gathering relevant information. A sample size of 41 participants was selected for the FGD, and 9 participants were drawn for the IDI, using purposive sampling technique. Thematic analysis method was used in analysing the data generated, which was used in answering the research questions. The study found out that journalists who cover the Boko Haram insurgency in the North East adopted various local and international best safety practices laid down for journalists covering dangerous assignments. The findings further revealed that media organizations do not provide safety measures for journalists and that the safety of journalists covering the Boko Haram insurgency in the North East is solely their responsibility. The research concludes that the issue of safety and protection of journalists in Nigeria must be given due consideration by the government and media stakeholders. The way and manner journalists lose their lives in the process of discharging their duty is alarming. The study has methodological limitations, the sample may not allow generalization of results and therefore recommends that further study can use quantitative approaches with a larger sample that could allow generalisation of results.

Keywords: Media, Journalist, Safety, Insurgency and Boko Haram

INTRODUCTION

Journalists' safety worldwide, in recent years is a thing of concern among key media players. Most journalists who report in risky environments consider many uncertainties and dangers to be inherent in their work as they face many security threats that can be mitigated. Worldwide, within the past two decades about 1149 journalists have been killed with confirmed motives. Over sixty percent (60%) of these cases were classified as murder, meaning; the targeted killing of journalists in relation to their work (IFJ 2014, CPJ 2015 and UNESCO 2016). The Committee to Protect Journalists documented 1387 killings of journalists since 1992, 713 out of which were unsolved with perpetrators enjoying complete impunity (Zuffova and Carlini 2021).

This according to Ulla (2016) was as a result of the drastic decline in freedom of information and safety of journalists during this period. Simultaneously, Press freedom index for 2015

declares that press freedom is declining worldwide and points out the targeting and manipulation of media workers as the main cause of this deterioration (RSF, 2015).

Two-thirds of the one hundred and eighty (180) countries surveyed for 2015 World Press freedom index, performed less well than in previous year. The annual global indicator which measures the overall level of violations of freedom of information and that of journalists' safety in one hundred and eighty (180) countries year by year, has risen to 3,719, an eight percent (8%) increase over 2014 and almost Ten percent (10%) compared with 2013. In 2014, Eighty-Seven (87) cases of killings of journalists were recorded. The ongoing armed conflict in Syria has continued to inflict a high toll on journalists' lives with Ten (10) journalists killed in Syria, eight (8) in Palestine, six (6) in Iraq, five (5) in Libya, five (5) in Afghanistan and Seven (7) in Ukraine, this decline affected all continents (UNESCO, 2015, Ming –Kuck, 2015, Ulla, 2016).

According to the CPJ (2017), 'at least Forty-seven (47) journalists were killed in the course of their work in 2017'. There is no uniformity among nations and governments on the treatment of journalists. The CPJ analysis indicates that, Iraq with Eight (8) killings Syria with seven (7) and Mexico with six (6) killings were the worst places for reporters in 2017.

Between 2018 and March 2021, about One Hundred and seventeen (117) journalists were killed, these killings were confirmed Murder and crossfire in the course of their duty. A year-by-year distribution of these death shows that 2018 was the worst for the safety of journalists worldwide with Fifty-six (56) deaths, twenty-six (26) cases in 2019, Thirty-two (32) deaths in 2020 and three (3) journalists have been killed in the first quarter of 2021(CPJ, 2021). The 2020 world press Index compiled by Reporters Without Borders (RSF) showed that the coming decade will be decisive for the future of journalism, with the COVID 19 pandemic highlighting and amplifying the many crises that threaten the right to free report, independent, diverse and reliable information (RSF, 2020).

Reporters Without Borders further maintained that journalists and news organisations are indispensable partners in the exercise of this basic freedom. This informs why those who seek to restrict the public right to information target journalists. This usually jeopardizes their safety as they (those that muzzle the press) go to any extent to silence them. The number of journalists killed while on duty (over 700 since 2006 to 2014) shows the scale of the problem and the difficulty in dealing with it.

In Nigeria, safety of journalists is not significantly different from the global experience. Nigeria is also committed to protecting and promoting the rights and safety of media professionals. But, that notwithstanding, journalists are still vulnerable to psychological harm, physical abuse and death (including murder). Commonly, they encounter acts of impunity like indiscriminate arrests and detention without charge; intimidation and harassment by security operatives; threats of arrest, and seizures of publications and working tools such as cameras, computers and machines. Other acts include: closure of offices by the police or Department of State Security; abductions and kidnappings by militant groups; violence, battering and killing; bombing of offices and prevention from carrying out duties especially in public places; exploitation and abuse of judicial processes against journalists and judicial harassment (Pate et al, 2017). Wilson (2015) states that journalists working in conflict zones like the North East and politically volatile areas remain highly vulnerable to attacks without investigations or arrest of perpetrators, except for condemnations that usually follow from the Nigeria Union of Journalists (NUJ), the most visible media pressure union. Journalists in Nigeria continue to suffer harassment and intimidation even outside the coverage of conflict.

The killing of Dele Giwa; journalist, editor and founder of News Watch magazine in 1986 by a parcel bomb sent to his home, was a clear case of murder. It was the first time a journalist had been killed in that manner. Since then, it has been killings, harassment, and arrests one after the other. The 27th April, 2012 same day bombing of two newspaper Houses in Abuja and Kaduna in which nine (9) people lost their lives count as a notable attack on journalists. The bombing was linked to a This Day newspaper report on the activities of Boko Haram. Pate and Oso (2017) in their analysis of the activities of Boko Haram insurgency concluded that, 'The Boko Haram terrorism and violent extremism that ravaged the North-East Nigeria from 2009 to date had exposed weakness in the safety policy and protocols for local journalists in times and zones of tension in Nigeria'. However, journalists that covered the zone have demonstrated great resilience to major risks, threats, and death with severe consequences on their freedom and professional integrity. Over these years of insurgency, five (5) journalists were killed and many injured in the zone. (Pate and Oso, 2017, Mu'azu 2015). Between 2019 and 2020, two (2) journalists; Onifade Emmanuel of Gboah TV and Precious Owolabi of Channels TV were murdered in the course of their duties (CPJ, 2020).

In view of the foregoing background, this study seeks to examine journalists' safety in covering Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria, with a particular reference to the three worst hit states of Borno, Yobe and Adamawa.

The aim of the study is to examine the role media organisations play in ensuring journalists' safety in the coverage of Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria. Its specific objective is to find out safety measures media organisations provide for journalists covering Boko Haram Insurgency.

METHODOLOGY

The Research Procedures for selecting participants and collecting and analysing data are described in this section. A qualitative research approach was used in getting valuable data for this research. A qualitative research approach was chosen because it is especially useful in discovering the meaning that people give to events that they experience (Merriam, 1998). Focus Group Discussion, and in-depth interview methods were used for data collection. Focus Group Discussion was used to elicit information from practicing journalists who cover Boko Haram insurgency, while in-depth interviews were conducted among media Heads in the three States which the scope of this research covers; Borno, Yobe and Adamawa. These two methods were considered most appropriate in view of the research topic.

Qualitative approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study, in that it takes into consideration the social factors that are present in the area of study. Most importantly, the qualitative approach contributed in addressing the aim and objectives of this study and answering the research questions. This research is about journalists' safety in covering Boko Haram Insurgency in the North East, and to do that there is a need to look beyond the surface of the argument, but look deeply into the meanings that can be understood from the data, and that is one thing that a qualitative approach offered.

For the in-depth interview, nine (9) participants who included senior editors and media Heads were selected. While the Focus Group Discussion was based on open ended questions basically of the research questions which elicited substantial responses from the discussants. In doing this, the discussions were done in two rounds of FGD consisting of a minimum of six discussants in every session in the states where the research covered.

- **Population and Sample**

The population of this study is the entire journalists who work in Borno, Adamawa and Yobe States. In order to achieve the objectives of this study; a sample size of 50 participants among the selected journalists working in the three states was drawn. nineteen (19) respondents from Borno, sixteen (16) from Yobe and fifteen (15) from Adamawa, these areas were selected for the purpose of relevance in view of the topic under study.

The research adopted the purposive sampling technique in selecting journalists working in the three states, it is a form of a non-probability sampling technique. This technique entails the researcher deliberately selecting what forms his/her sample based on some predetermined purposes or aim which the study hopes to achieve. Journalists who covered Boko Haram Insurgency in Borno, Adamawa and Yobe were selected as participants in this study since they would be “knowledgeable informants” (Lincoln & Guba, 1985, p. 234). Because the goal of the study was to uncover challenges of journalist’s safety in covering Boko Haram Insurgency in the North East.

The FGDs were conducted for two groups of not less than six (6) people in each session, in the three states. An in-depth interview was conducted with 3 media Heads of media outfits in each of the states.

- **Method of Data Collection.**

The research adopted two techniques of data collection; in-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion. In-depth interview, according to Carolyn (2006) is, “a qualitative research technique that involves conducting intensive individual interviews with a small number of respondents to explore their perspective. To him, in-depth interview provides much more detailed information than what is available through other data collection methods, such as survey. The data collection procedure for the focus group involved the use of audio recorder, observation of nonverbal communication issues and note taking. At the commencement of the focus group, the researcher explained the study, its purpose, the role of the moderator and his assistant, use of the digital audio tape recorders and how their responses would be confidential through the use of pseudonyms to the participants before the latter’s, took over the session. The study used a semi-structured focus group guide to lead the discussion and keep it in line with the topic. At the end of the focus group, the research assistant provided a summary of the major points of the discussion and gave the participants the chance to confirm or clarify any of these points. This summary technique, according to Lewis et al in Dawn (2011), will confirm that the participants feel their thoughts are well interpreted by the researcher. For the in-depth interview, face-to-face semi-structured interview was used as the procedure of data collection. It is an informal guided form of interview where formed topics are provided by the researcher to enable the participants discuss them under the guidance of the researcher. Bjournholt and Farstad (2012) pointed out that semi-structured interview can help in the production of rich information, including observational data. It is a technique that allows new ideas to be brought up during the interview.

A paper-based interview guide was developed. The responses of the participants during the interview session were recorded with audio recording gadgets, alongside the interview guide which served as major instrument for data collection. Face-to-face interview provides synchronous communication of time and place and has advantage of social cues such as voice, intonation, body language and so on (Bjournholt and Farstad, 2012). The interviewee can give the interviewer a lot of extra information that can be added to the verbal answer of the researcher on a question, using open-ended questions and discussions may diverge from the

guide. The audio recorder allows accuracy of the data collection and good conversational flow. Jotting materials like pen and paper were used to back-up in case of technical fault by the audio recorder. This ruled out any possibility of information loss due to technical hitches.

- **The Validity and Reliability**

In an effort to ensure that reliability and validity are achieved, the study employed qualitative research methods and also recruits research assistant who are conversant with the profession of journalism. Notebooks and radio cassette recorders were used, notebook was used taking notes and the audio was used for recording of all the sessions.

In an effort to ensure credibility, the researcher employed the use of multiple methods of data collection. The use of Focus Group Discussion and in-depth interview and with the review of existing works related to this study suggest that the topic was examined from different perspectives which would help build confidence in the findings. Another means employed by the researcher to achieve credibility of the study, is to account for all sort of biases which may influence findings. For instance, personal judgment of the researcher and sampling biases are explained in detail in order to provide critical reflection of the methods used; and this strategy is key to having “sufficient and relevance of data collection and analysis” of qualitative research (Sendelowski, 1993).

- **Method of Data Presentation/ Analysis.**

Analysing the data, the study adopted a thematic analysis approach, this involves becoming immersed in the material, producing a thematically ordered account supported by material quoted from transcripts. The recorded information from the participants was transcribed manually into documents to facilitate thematic analysis. For analysing the findings, the audio recordings, field notes with descriptions of any non-verbal cues and other observations were reviewed.

Thematic analysis is a categorizing strategy for qualitative data. It is a data analytic strategy that helps the researcher move his analysis from a broader reading of the data towards discovering patterns and developing themes. Boyatzis (1998) explains thematic analysis as a process of “encoding qualitative information”. Thus the researcher developed “codes” words or phrases that serve as labels for sections of data.

- **Data Presentation and Analysis**

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the challenges journalists face in covering Boko Haram insurgency in the North East. Participants’ experiences and feedback added insight to the research questions posed in this study. By listening to and analysing the experiences of these journalists, valuable information was obtained about safety measures journalists adopted in covering the Boko Haram activities and on whether media organisations provide safety measures and safety kits to their reporters. As such, the data obtained from the interviewee were presented with supporting evidences, including both quotations and feedback.

The data was analysed as follows:

- **Safety measures/Kits media organisations provide for journalists covering Boko Haram Insurgency**

This question intends to find out from journalists and the media managers whether media organizations make provisions and put up safety measures to ensure their reporters in the field covering Boko Haram insurgency in the North East are safe from all forms of danger. Also, to verify and cross examine the information gathered from journalists themselves on this issue.

The data generated from the in-depth interview held with media managers in the three states, revealed that, media organisations do not provide safety measures for journalists covering Boko Haram insurgency. Almost all the participants in the FGDs, about (95%) commented with disappointment when asked whether their employers and media organizations provided measures for their safety. In their similar and unanimous response, Participant 9 said; ‘I needed protective gear after a training in South Africa, unfortunately, my employer did not get these items for me. All they wanted was for you to write stories. From my findings most Nigerian media companies do not provide capacity building for their journalists.’ In support of participant 9 position. Participant 40 expressed his experiences; ‘In 2017, I was gifted a bag of protective gear by a colleague who I met at a training workshop.’ Other participants complained about poor welfare for journalists reporting from conflict zone. Participant 17 who said; ‘I had to buy Camera to do this work, from my savings out of the little monthly salary which had even been halved due to the Covid-19 pandemic.’ He added; ‘Nobody also cares about providing hazard allowance for journalists like me reporting from a conflict zone. Salaries are not paid timely let alone hazard allowance.’

Media managers who were interviewed during the In-depth interview, complained of funding and lack of commercials which are the major sources of revenue. One of the managers, participant 49 said; ‘We are surviving by Allah’s grace, we rely on government patronage, high cost of diesel is making us run at lost, since electricity is not reliable. We are doing our best in ensuring our reporters are safe in the field while discharging their duties.’ Another participant opened up by saying; ‘We have this challenge as an industry, we cannot afford the resources to send reporters on training and get them safety kits. Paying salary is difficult and that is the reality of the Nigerian media industry.’

FINDINGS

- 1, The study discovered that, journalists adopt various local and international best safety practices laid down for journalists covering dangerous assignments.
2. The findings of the study revealed that, media organizations do not provide safety measures for journalists, and that the safety of journalists covering Boko Haram insurgency in the North East is solely the journalists’ responsibility.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In this paper, data analysis and findings of the research were reported. Hence, for the purpose of this paper, discussion will be based on only the findings reported.

The interviews (Focus Group Discussion and In-depth interview) were analysed. Data analysis related to research question 1 revealed two themes, and four categories which formed our basis of discussion below:

The first finding of the study aligns with the first objective of this study which seeks to identify the safety measures journalists who cover Boko Haram insurgency put in place. The finding discovered that, journalists adopt various local and international best safety practices laid down for journalists covering dangerous assignments. This finding highlighted four distinct safety measures adopted by journalists covering Boko Haram Insurgency. These measures include;

- i. Undergoing Hostile environment and first aid training conducted by ex-military officers.

- ii. Conducting thorough and regular risk assessments which they say include; emergency communication protocol with colleagues, family members and their Organisations.
- iii. Risk analyses and contingency planning.
- iv. Situational awareness which is emphasized when going on field especially when there is a bomb blast or attack on villages or communities, they wear bulletproof and Helmet as safety and security measures. Two themes from the data supports this finding.

This finding validates a similar study conducted by Pate and Idris (2016) on professionalism and Risk management among journalists covering Boko Haram insurgency, which they concluded that, “between 2009 and 2015 four journalists were killed and many threatened by Boko Haram insurgents, that the safety of journalists in that region was solely the responsibility of individual journalists. However, their study did not uncover details of how journalists themselves were responsible for their safety. This study filled that gap by identifying the safety measures put in place by these journalists on their own to ensure they carry out their duty of covering the activities of the Boko Haram insurgents.

The finding also resolved part of the gap in the literature, because most studies in the area concentrated on identifying safety measures for journalists covering conflict and war, the nature of safety challenges, others looked at the after effects of this challenge on journalists. Enough studies have not been done on examining the efficacy of these safety measures and protocols developed for journalists. This study was able to measure the efficacy and workability of the safety protocols. Journalists in the field who adopted these protocols confirmed during the FGDs that, these safety routine measures they carryout reduced the perceived risk of covering Boko Haram activities, that the more safety measures they put in place the more confident and safer they become and as such the measures were effective and reduced risk.

There also lies a connection between this finding and one of the assumptions of the Protection motivation theory posited by Rogers (1983), Rogers asserts that, “People protect themselves among other factors based on the perceived severity of threatening events and the efficacy of recommended preventive protocol and self-efficacy” Efficacy is the individual expectancy that carrying out recommendations can remove the threat. Self-efficacy is the believe in one’s ability to execute the recommended course of action successfully. Participant 21 described his perception of reduced risk and improved safety after the safety routine measures in the following words, “These skills have made me remained hopeful, and resolute, my fear has gone because with all the skills, knowledge, and experience gotten from the safety protocols and the safety kits with me, I am sure that at least risk has reduced and I feel safe when I have no much cause to fear while in the field.”

The study also found that, media organisations do not provide safety measures and safety kits to their reporters who cover Boko Haram insurgency. These journalists are sent to cover risky assignments and are solely responsible for their safety. The data generated from both the FGDs and IDIs showed that both the journalists and the media managers agree to this fact. The implication of this finding is that, journalists are deliberately exposed to danger even by their employers. Hence, media organisations are culprit and part of the problems journalists face in the course of discharging their duty of informing the public. Participants mentioned how they save money from their salary which are not regularly paid to buy gadgets for their work.

The finding concurs with the findings of Gachie 2013, Arulchelven 2015, Pate and Idris 2016 who observed that apart from the challenges in the field journalists also face internal safety challenges with their employers. Pate and Idris (2016) further concluded in their study on professionalism and Risk management among journalists covering Boko Haram insurgency

that; 'the security and safety of journalists in that region were solely the responsibility of individual journalists. The study also exposed the inadequacies of both the government and media owners in the provision of protection for journalists at war zones.

CONCLUSION

Although, this paper presents just a report of two research question., The study has done something different in terms of the methodology, because many similar studies' approach to data collection and analysis were basically the use of structured questionnaire. This may lead to a shift in the outcome of previous studies.

This research has enriched the literature in this area by providing useful professional and academic information on the state of journalists' safety and the lapses in the provisions of our laws on freedom of expression and that of journalists' safety. Further studies may look at the theoretical underpinning of this area of research as most theories do not adequately explain the phenomenon.

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